

The Influence of Servant Leadership, Self-Awareness, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Employee Performance in Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Timur

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the influence of servant leadership, self-awareness, and organizational citizenship behavior on employee performance at Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Timur. The research was conducted using a quantitative approach and data were collected through questionnaires distributed to employees. The data obtained was analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) PLS method using Smart PLS Version 4.0 software. The respondents used in this study were 79 employees out of a total of 97 employees at Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Timur. The data collection instrument measured on a Likert scale. The findings revealed that servant leadership, self-awareness, and organizational citizenship behavior have a significant positive influence on employee performance. These results highlight the importance of fostering servant leadership qualities, promoting self-awareness, and encouraging organizational citizenship behavior in improving employee performance at Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Timur.

I. INTRODUCTION

Civil Servants (ASN) play a crucial role in carrying out government tasks and serving the public. Therefore, the quality of ASN performance is extremely crucial for the success and sustainability of public services. In today's competitive work environment, employee performance is a key factor in achieving organizational goals. In the context of public service, ASN employees have an important role in providing quality services to the public. To achieve optimal performance, the role of leadership, self-awareness, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) need to be considered

Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah (Bappeda) is a government institution in Indonesia that is responsible for formulating policies and programs for regional development. BAPPEDA is an important institution in regional development as it has the task of planning, coordinating, and evaluating regional development programs and activities in accordance with the vision and mission of the local government. Due to the importance of these tasks, employee performance is a key factor in carrying out better planning. The phenomenon occurring in Bappeda Province, OCB, seems to have become a culture among the employees. Without being asked, employees often volunteer to assist their coworkers in completing their tasks. Additionally, certain leadership traits in various units appear to influence their work methods and performance. Therefore, it is important to conduct research to determine whether employees here consciously help their coworkers and if leadership characteristics such as servant leadership can affect their performance. Employee performance can be influenced by various factors such as self-awareness, leadership, and OCB. Good leadership can provide guidance and support to employees in achieving organizational goals and strengthen employee commitment to the organization. Additionally, with high self-awareness among employees, it is expected to enhance performance, especially in developing better planning for the country, specifically in East Java Province.

Research conducted by Taufiqur Rachman, Siti Mujanah, and Nanis Susanti (2020) indicates that Servant Leadership and Self Awareness significantly influence Employee Performance. A study by Wiwiek Harwiki (2013) shows that Servant Leadership has an impact on employee performance but does not affect OCB. Research by Mariman Darto, Djoko Setyadi, Sukisno S. Riadi, and Sugeng Hariyadi (2015) demonstrates that OCB has a positive influence on Employee Performance. on another research by Uswatun Hasanah, Siti Mujanah (2020) shows that that the increase in the level of self-awareness is not able to encourage an increase in employee performance. So that the results of this study contradict the results of research by (Putri, Tazkiyah and Amelia, 2019) and Harianto (2011) that shows self awareness have significant effect on employee performance. Therefore, this research is important to reexamine whether employee performance is influenced by OCB, Servant Leadership, and Self Awareness, as well as whether Servant Leadership and Self Awareness affect employees' OCB behavior, particularly within BAPPEDA of East Java Province.

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II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Human Resource Management

According to Mangkunegara (2013:2), human resource management is a systematic and strategic approach to managing human resources within an organization. Human Resource Management involves various activities such as workforce planning, employee selection, training and development, performance management, and compensation management. According to Hasibuan (2013), human resource management is a field of knowledge and art related to managing human resources within an organization. According to him, the main objective of human resource management is to maximize the contribution of human resources in achieving organizational goals effectively and efficiently. Both authors state that human resource management should be integrated with the overall business strategy of the organization. Additionally, Human Resource Management should consider aspects such as balancing the needs of the organization and employees, fulfilling employees' rights, and applying ethical principles in managing human resources.

Overall, the author's perspective above regarding Human Resource Management is in line with the views of other human resource management experts, which is that Human Resource Management is a strategic and integrated approach to managing human resources within an organization, with the goal of achieving organizational objectives effectively and efficiently.

B. Servant Leadership

Servant leadership theory is an approach to leadership that focuses on serving others. This theory was developed by Robert K. Greenleaf in the 1970s. According to Greenleaf, a true leader is someone who prioritizes the needs and interests of others over their own personal interests.

According to experts, some characteristics of servant leadership are Empathy which mean Ability to understand and address the feelings and needs of others. Humility mean Prioritizing the interests of others and displaying humility. Empowerment mean Providing autonomy and responsibility to individuals based on their abilities. Building relationships mean Developing trusting relationships and fostering collaboration. Performance enhancement mean Improving organizational performance by leveraging the potential of team members. Service which mean Having a strong service orientation and offering support to others.

The indicators used to assess servant leadership are as follows :

- a) Willingness to serve with Indicators seeking feedback from others, valuing others' viewpoints and ideas, not easily defensive or rejecting criticism,
- b) Openness with indicator seeking feedback from others, valuing others' viewpoints and ideas, not easily defensive or rejecting criticism,
- c) Emphaty with Indicator considering others' feelings and needs in decision-making, showing concern and sympathy towards others, building personal relationships with others,
- d) Trustworthiness with indicator fulfilling promises, maintaining confidentiality, not abusing the trust given.

C. Self Awareness

Self-awareness is the way an individual thinks about themselves, their authority, responsibilities, and goals in facing and resolving problems, enabling them to address the tasks and challenges they encounter. Therefore, one's self-awareness greatly influences their performance within an organization (Prabowo, 2014). Self-awareness can also be understood as continuous attention to one's inner state. When someone possesses good self-awareness, they can self-regulate, meaning they are capable of reading social situations to understand others and comprehend how others perceive them (Putri, Tazkiyah, & Amelia, 2019). According to Harianto (2011), in the field of psychology, self-awareness begins by looking at the terminology of the word "personal," which means oneself or independently. From there, we can understand that self-awareness is about knowing what needs to be done and why, based on the intelligence one possesses.

According to Baron, Bramscombe, and Byrne (2008), there are several forms of self-awareness, including:

- a) Subjective Self-Awareness: The individual's ability to distinguish oneself as an individual from their physical and social environment.
- b) Objective Self-Awareness: Individuals can become the object of their own attention, aware of their mental state, and knowing that they know and remember that they remember.
- c) Symbolic Self-Awareness: The individual's ability to form abstract concepts within themselves through language. This ability enables individuals to communicate, establish relationships, set goals, evaluate outcomes, and form attitudes related to themselves, as well as defend themselves from threatening communications.

D. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is part of the field of organizational behavior that is typically unseen or not formally accounted for. Robbins and Judge (2006) argue that OCB is discretionary behavior that is not part of the formal job requirements but supports the effective functioning of the organization. This behavior is also referred to as extra-role behavior. OCB also refers

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to behaviors that go beyond the normal obligations of employees. This includes avoiding unnecessary conflicts, helping others without expecting recognition, persevering in hard work, engaging in organizational activities, and performing tasks that exceed the normal assigned duties (McShane & Glinow, 2015).

Based on the definitions mentioned above, it can be concluded that the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is extra-role work behavior or behavior outside the required workload that is voluntary and sincere without any orders from the company. This behavior is very beneficial for companies, especially in corporate environments with very fierce business competition. According to Robbins and Judge (2013), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) consists of five dimensions, namely :

a) Altruism

Altruism refers to employees' voluntary behavior to assist coworkers and the organization as a whole. Indicators of this dimension include helping coworkers in difficulty, providing emotional support to stressed colleagues, and offering assistance to others without being asked.

b) Sportsmanship

Sportsmanship encompasses employees' behavior of accepting criticism, tolerating unfair situations, and not worsening a bad situation. Indicators of this dimension include accepting unfair decisions, responding calmly to criticism, and coping with uncertainty or difficult circumstances.

c) Civic Virtue

Civic virtue refers to employees' participation in organizational activities that are indirectly related to their primary job tasks. Indicators of this dimension include involvement in organizational activities, efforts to enhance the organization's image, and compliance with organizational rules.

d) Conscientiousness

Conscientiousness includes employees' behavior of performing their tasks well and being dedicated to achieving organizational goals. Indicators of this dimension include executing tasks to the best of their ability, going above and beyond what is expected, and ensuring that work is completed effectively.

e) Courtesy

Courtesy encompasses employees' behavior of being polite, friendly, and appreciative of their coworkers. Indicators of this dimension include respecting colleagues, being polite and friendly, and paying attention to politeness and ethics when interacting with coworkers.

E. Employee Performance

According to Mangkunegara (2016:67), the term "Performance" originates from the words "job performance" or "Actual Performance" (actual achievement of work performance by an individual). The definition of Performance is the quality and quantity of work results achieved by an employee in carrying out their tasks according to the responsibilities assigned to them. Performance is the outcome of a process that is referred to and measured over a specific period of time based on predetermined provisions or agreements (Edison, 2016:190). Generally, Performance can be defined as the overall working process of an individual, the results of which can be used as a basis to determine whether the individual's work is good or otherwise (Roziqin, 2010:41). Employee performance refers to what employees do and do not do that affects how much they contribute to the organization, including the quality of output, quantity of output, timeliness of output, attendance at the workplace, and cooperative attitude (Mathis, 2002:78). Employee performance is the work outcome over a specific period compared to various possibilities, such as standards, targets/objectives, or agreed-upon criteria (Maryoto, 2000:91).

There are 5 indicators to measure individual employee performance, namely :

a) Quality : Work quality is measured based on employees' perception of the quality of their work output and the completeness of tasks based on their skills and abilities.

b) Quantity : It refers to the amount of production expressed in units, such as the number of units or the number of activity cycles completed.

c) Timeliness : The level of completion of activities within the specified timeframe, considering coordination with output results and the optimal utilization of available time for other activities.

d) Effectiveness : The level of utilization of organizational resources (such as manpower, money, technology, and raw materials) enhanced to improve the outcomes of each resource utilization unit.

e) Independence : It represents the extent to which an employee can carry out their job functions. Work commitment: The level of commitment employees have towards their work in the organization and their responsibility for office tasks.

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III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure. 1 Conceptual Framework

H1: Hypothesis (H1): Servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior.

H2: Hypothesis (H2): Self Awareness has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior.

H3: Hypothesis (H3): Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance.

H4: Hypothesis (H4): Servant leadership has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance.

H5: Hypothesis (H5): Self Awareness has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Types and Sources

The type of this research is a quantitative approach emphasizing on testing theory by measuring variables and analyzing data using statistical procedures. This research used secondary data which were retrieved from October 2023.

B. Population

The research was conducted at Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Timur. This study used a quantitative approach, the population in this study includes civil servant employees, totaling 97 individuals. From the entire population, the sample size was calculated using the Slovin formula and proportional sampling at 5%, resulting in a sample size of 79 individuals

C. Data Collection

Questionnaires are used to collect data. In general, the scoring technique used in this research questionnaire is the Likert scale technique through 5 (five) levels with score weights 5 Strongly Agree to 1 Strongly Disagree

D. Data Analysis Method

Data analysis in this study uses Partial Least Square (PLS), which is an alternative method based on variants of the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method.

V. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Convergent validity in PLS with reflective indicators is assessed based on outer loading. The rule of thumb used for convergent validity is a loading factor > 0.50 and average variance extracted (AVE) > 0.50 (Chin, 1995 in Jogiyanto and Abdillah, 2014: 60). Evaluation of the convergent validity of the outer loading value on each indicator in Servant Leadership, Self-Awareness, OCB, and Performance variables can also be seen in Figure 2:

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Figure. 2 Outer Model

Another method to see discriminant validity is to look at the square root of average variance extracted (AVE) value. The recommended value is above 0.5. The following are the AVE values in this study:

Table. 1 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.876	0.884	0.901	0.534
Performance	0.898	0.901	0.918	0.584
Self Awareness	0.816	0.817	0.867	0.520
Servant Leadership	0.841	0.844	0.879	0.511

Source: Primary Data, Processed (2023)

The table above shows that all constructs have AVE values above 0.5; Likewise, the square root value of AVE gets a value of more than 0.5 so that it meets a good validity test standard.

After the estimated model meets the criteria for the Outer Model, then the structural model (Inner model) is tested as can be seen in the R-Square value in the construct in table 2

Table. 2 R-Square Result

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.637	0.627
Performance	0.723	0.712

Source: Primary Data, Processed (2023)

Table 2 shows the R Square value of 0.637 for the OCB construct, which means that Self Awareness, and Service Leadership can explain the OCB variance of 63.7%. The Performance construct has an R Square value of 0.723, which means that Self Awareness Service Leadership and OCB can explain the Performance variance of 72.3%.

The results of the path analysis calculations carried out by the smart-PLS program can be seen in Figure 3.

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Figure. 3 Path Analysis SmartPLS

Table. 3 Hypothesis Result

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Result
Organizational Citizenship Behavior -> Performance	0.374	0.388	0.123	3.037	0.002	Significant
Self Awareness -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.441	0.436	0.118	3.749	0.000	Significant
Self Awareness -> Performance	0.230	0.232	0.105	2.188	0.029	Significant
Servant Leadership -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.395	0.404	0.111	3.568	0.000	Significant
Servant Leadership -> Performance	0.316	0.304	0.118	2.691	0.007	Significant

Source: Primary Data, Processed (2023)

Servant Leadership has a significant effect on OCB (H1)

The results of the calculations in table 3 indicate that Servant Leadership has a positive effect of 0.395 on OCB. This influence is accompanied by a Tstatistic of 3.568 (Tstat> 1.96). Based on this, then H1 is accepted or in other words, Servant Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the OCB of Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur. Thus, the increase in Servant Leadership will also encourage an increase in OCB. This is like what Taufiqur Rachman, Siti Mujanah, and Nanis Susanti (2020) said that Servant Leadership significantly influence Employee Performance.

Self Awareness has a significant effect on OCB (H2)

The results of the calculations in table 3 show that self-awareness has a positive effect of 0.441 on OCB. This influence is accompanied by a Tstatistic of 3.749 (Tstat> 1.96). Based on this, then H2 is accepted, or in other words, Self-awareness has a positive and significant impact on the OCB of of Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur. Thus, an increase in the level of self-awareness will also encourage an increase in OCB to the employees of the Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur. The results of this study support Taufiqur Rachman, Siti Mujanah, and Nanis Susanti (2020) said that Self Awareness significantly influence Employee Performance.

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Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) has a significant effect on Employee Performance (H3)

The results of the calculations in table 3 show that OCB has a positive effect of 0.374 on Employee Performance. This influence is accompanied by a Tstatistic of 3.037 ($Tstat > 1.96$). Based on this, then H3 is accepted, or in other words, OCB has a positive and significant impact on the Employee Performance of of Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur. Thus, an increase in the level of OCB will also encourage an increase on Employee Performance to the employees of the Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur. The results of this study is different from A study by Wiwiek Harwiki (2013) shows that employee performance does not affect by OCB. But this result support another research by Research by Mariman Darto, Djoko Setyadi, Sukisno S. Riadi, and Sugeng Hariyadi (2015) demonstrates that OCB has a positive influence on Employee Performance.

Servant Leadership has a significant effect on Employee Performance (H4)

The results of the calculations in table 3 indicate that Servant Leadership has a positive effect of 0.316 on Employee Performance. This influence is accompanied by a Tstatistic of 2.691 ($Tstat > 1.96$). Based on this, then H4 is accepted or in other words, Servant Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the Employee Performance of Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur. Thus, the increase in Servant Leadership will also encourage an increase on Employee Performance. This is like what Taufiqur Rachman, Siti Mujanah, and Nanis Susanti (2020) said that Servant Leadership significantly influence Employee Performance. and also Support study by Uswatun Hasanah, Siti Mujanah (2020) that shows increasing Servant Leadership levels will also encourage increased performance in employees

Self Awareness has a significant effect on Employee Performance (H5)

The results of the calculations in table 3 show that self-awareness has a positive effect of 0.230 on Employee Performance. This influence is accompanied by a Tstatistic of 2.188 ($Tstat > 1.96$). Based on this, then H5 is accepted, or in other words, Self-awareness has a positive impact on the Employee Performance of of Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur. Thus, an increase in the level of self-awareness will also increase to the employees performance of the Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur. The result contradict study by Uswatun Hasanah, Siti Mujanah (2020) that shows the increase in the level of self-awareness is not able to encourage an increase in employee performance. but results of this study support the results of research by (Putri, Tazkiyah and Amelia, 2019) and Harianto (2011) that shows self awareness have significant effect on employee performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research examining the influence of Servant Leadership, Self Awareness, Organizational Citizenship Behaviors (OCB) on employee performance at Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Timur (Bappeda Provinsi Jawa Timur), it can then be concluded that Servant Leadership has a positive and significant effect on OCB and Employee Performance, Self Awareness has a significant effect on OCB and Employee Performance. Organizational Citizenship Behaviors (OCB) has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance.

This study supports several previous studies, but there are also contradictory findings compared to earlier research from Uswatun Hasanah, Siti Mujanah (2020) that shows the increase in the level of self-awareness is not able to encourage an increase in employee performance. And the research from Wiwiek Harwiki (2013) that shows employee performance does not affect by OCB. indicating that indeed the conditions in the workplace may differ from other workplaces. However, in Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah (Bappeda) Provinsi Jawa Timur, employee performance is indeed influenced by servant leadership, self-awareness, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Furthermore, OCB is also formed, in part, by self-awareness and the presence of a servant leadership figure.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings in this study, Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Timur can increase employee performance by paying attention to lead through servant leadership, instilling self-awareness and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). These results highlight the importance of fostering servant leadership qualities, promoting self-awareness, and encouraging organizational citizenship behavior in improving employee performance at Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Timur. Suggestions for further research can examine other variables such as teamwork, motivation, work ethic, competence, compensation, and another types of leadership such as spiritual leadership and transactional leadership and other variables that can improve employee performance. and for future research In the future research, it is expected to increase the sample size not only from one government agency but also from several others, in order to provide insights into the overall performance of government employees in East Java.

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